

Popular Article

Paracetamol Toxicity in Pet Animals

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Introduction

Paracetamol (Acetaminophen) is a synthetic non-opiate derivative of P-aminophenol, a NSAIDs commonly used in human medicine for its antipyretic and analgesic action (Court and David, 1997). Paracetamol toxicity is quite common in cats and dogs compared to other species due to the oral administration by the owner or accidental ingestion by the animal itself. There is no safe dose of paracetamol for cats and thus its toxicity is more common in cats as compared to dogs. The toxic dose is reported as 50-100 mg/kg b.wt, but a dose as small as 10 mg/kg b.wt has produced signs of toxicity and death (Aronson and Drobatz, 1996). Cats are relatively deficient in activity of the enzyme glucuronyl transferase which conjugates Paracetamol to glucuronic acid for excretion.

Paracetamol is not licensed for veterinary usage in United States of America, but is certainly used off label. It is licensed in Europe for oral route in dogs (combined with codeine phosphate) and in pigs (Anonymous, 1999). Various forms are available like tablets, capsules, suspensions, intravenous and intramuscular forms (Pothiappan et. al., 2014).

Toxicological Mechanism of Action

Paracetamol brings the pharmacological action by inhibiting cyclooxygenase (COX). In mammal's paracetamol (acetaminophen) is bio transformed to nontoxic products in the liver via conjugation with glucuronic acid and excreted by the kidneys. A small portion of paracetamol is metabolized through the cytochrome P-450 enzyme pathway producing a metabolite, N-acetyl-para-benzoquinoneimine (**NAPQI**) which is highly toxic. Paracetamol exposure becomes toxic, when glucuronidation and sulfation pathways become saturated. NAPQI binds to cellular proteins and membranes and leads to cellular injury and death, particularly hepatocytes (Allen, 2003).

NAPQI also causes severe oxidative stress to red blood cells. The oxidant damage to heme ions results in methemoglobin. Ferrous iron is oxidized to ferric iron converting hemoglobin to methemoglobin, which does not carry oxygen (Perry et. al., 1998 and Aaronson, 2000). Oxidation of hemoglobin may also cause Heinz body formation (Perry et. al., 1998).

Cats are extremely sensitive to the toxic effects of paracetamol, since the conjugation of glucuronides with many toxic compounds occurs slowly in cats. This is due to little possession of glucuronyl transferases. Deficiency of the glucuronide conjugation pathway results in more drug being conjugated to sulfates; however, the sulfation pathway is also lower in cats than other species (Allen, 2003).

Fig. Paracetamol (Acetaminophen, APAP) metabolic pathway (Yoon, E. et. al., 2016).

Clinical Signs

- ✓ Paracetamol poisoning is commonly presented with clinical signs of anorexia, dullness, facial and paw edema, muddy mucous membranes, respiratory distress and hematuria (Pothiappan et al., 2014).
- ✓ Large doses Paracetamol mainly causes liver injury along with renal dysfunction due to direct renal tubular dysfunction, possibly by affecting membrane protein function (Murphy, 2008).

Diagnosis

- ❖ Based on the history
- ❖ Based on clinical Signs
- ❖ Indicative of hepatic damage
- ❖ Lab diagnosis: elevation of the liver enzymes and kidney function tests.

Treatment

The goals of treatment are to decrease paracetamol absorption, increase its elimination, limit NAPQI formation, supplement glutathione stores, and provide supportive care (Wallace et. al., 2002).

- ❖ Initially, activated charcoal at a dose of 1-3 g/kg adsorbs acetaminophen.
- ❖ The specific antidote for the paracetamol toxicity is N- acetyl cysteine at the dose rate of 140 mg /kg as intravenously as loading dose after that 70 mg/kg intravenously or orally every 6 hrs for 5 times. N- acetyl cysteine is directly bind to the metabolites of paracetamol and enhance the elimination. It also derive as a glutathione precursor (Pothiappan et. al., 2014).

- ❖ Ascorbic acid (vitamin C) provides a reserve system for the reduction of methemoglobin back to hemoglobin (Perry et. al., 1998 and Osweiler, 1997).
- ❖ Cimetidine, the dose is 5-10 mg/kg PO, IM, or IV every 6-8 hours in dogs and cats (Plumb, 1999).
- ❖ Oxygen supplementation may require patients clinical for methemoglobinemia.
- ❖ Antibiotics and supportive fluid therapy is required for the acute kidney injury.

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